

Adsorption of cationic dyes ethidium bromide and methylene blue individually as well as from their binary mixture on silica

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The adsorption behaviours of the cationic dyes, ethidium bromide (EB) and methylene blue (MB) individually as well as from their 1 : 1 (mol/mol) binary mixture on negative surface of silica in aqueous medium have been investigated. The effects of temperature, the salt KCl and pH on the said adsorption process have been also examined. The results have been analyzed in terms of Langmuir equation wherever applicable. An assessment of the comparative adsorption of EB and MB under the studied conditions in terms of the energetics of the process has been attempted.

The phenomenon of adsorption has relevance in physical, analytical and biochemistry as well as in biology¹. It has relevance also in environmental pollution and protection with reference to water and waste treatment². Removal of toxic materials, hazardous ions and dyes from industrial effluents by way of adsorption is of great significance in connection with environmental and human-health safety. The adsorption by solids decreases the toxicity of the waste water or removes non-safe organic materials from industrial effluents, etc.^{3,4}

Silica can be used as an adsorbent in food, beverage, pharmaceuticals and chemical industries as well as used in municipal water supply and environmental control. Effluents from plants in dyeing industries contain highly coloured species; such highly coloured wastes are not only aesthetically displeasing but also hinder light penetration and may in consequence upset biological processes in rivers. In addition, dyes are toxic to some organisms and hence harmful to aquatic animals. Compared to activated charcoal, silica is a cheap and commercially available material that has potential in the treatment of effluents. It has a well defined surface structure and is a soil component⁵. Its surface has siloxane groups (Si-O-Si) and silanol groups (Si-OH)⁶. Silica can be crystalline (quartz) or amorphous (fused silica) and can be hydrophobic (with siloxane Si-O-Si groups) or hydrophilic (with silanol Si-OH groups)⁷. The hydrophobic-hydrophilic balance of silica surface can be controlled by physical and chemical treatment⁸⁻¹⁰. When exposed to water for an extended period of time, hydroxylation of the groups continue producing polymeric chains of -Si(OH)₂-O-Si(OH)₂-OH type that link up in different ways forming a three-dimensional network called silica gel¹¹. The negatively charged silica in water¹²⁻¹⁹ is ex-

pected to readily adsorb cationic dyes²⁰⁻²², like other negatively charged inorganic solids, e.g. glass²³ and montmorillonite²⁴⁻²⁷. Gibbs and Ritchie²⁰ examined the rate of adsorption of methylene blue on lochaline sand, powdered quartz and vitresil (ground vitreous silica). Plesch and Robertson²⁷ suggested that a typical basic dye (methylene blue) is adsorbed by montmorillonite following ion-exchange and physical adsorption. Several authors observed that silica has little or no adsorption potential for anionic dyes although Haldeman and Emmett²² prepared silica gels with adsorption properties for specific azo dyes. Parida and Mishra²⁸ studied the adsorption behaviours of styryl pyridium dyes on silica gel and explained the results in terms of a monolayer forming phenomenon.

In most adsorption experiments, the behaviours of the individual dyes are studied separately. They are hardly used in combination. In practical situation, several adsorbates may be present in solution requiring the importance of fundamental adsorption experiments on mixed adsorbate/adsorbent systems. This has prompted us to investigate the adsorption behaviours of ethidium bromide and methylene blue individually and in combination (1 : 1 mol/mol) on silica surface under different environmental conditions. A comparison of the basic adsorption properties of these two dyes, individually and in combination, has been made on thermodynamic ground. It may be mentioned that we have very recently investigated the adsorption of mixed dyes of methylene blue and methyl orange on cellulose²⁹, and that of amino acids (DL-tryptophan and L-histidine) on solid surfaces³⁰. It is hoped that the basic understanding on the adsorption of mixed adsorbates on solid surface herein studied would add to the knowledge of the interfacial adsorption phenomenon of multiadsorbate/adsorbent systems.

Results and Discussion

Adsorption of pure EB and MB from aqueous solution: The adsorption isotherms for EB at different temperatures on silica surface are illustrated in Fig. 1. The extents of adsorption at 30 and 35° are equal; at 40° the process has enhanced and, thereafter, decreases at temperatures 50 and 55° according to the normal expectation³¹.

Fig. 1. Adsorption isotherm for EB-silica system in aqueous medium at different temperatures : (1) 328, (2) 323, (3) 303 and 318, (4) 313 K.

The adsorption of pure MB (Fig. 2) systematically increases from 30–40°. At 40 and 50°, the extents of adsorption are equal, which declines at 55°. Both EB and MB have shown same kinds of feature of increasing adsorption in the lower range of the studied temperatures.

Fig. 2. Adsorption isotherm for MB-silica system in aqueous medium at different temperatures : (1) 328, (2) 303, (3) 308, (4) 313 and 323 K.

Normally, adsorption of gases is an exothermic process. Some systems may, however, show a reverse temperature effect³², i.e. increase of adsorption with increasing temperature. For adsorption on solid from solution, Bikerman³³

attributed the reverse adsorption behaviour to a negative temperature coefficient of the solubility of the solute or to a rapid simultaneous desorption of the solvent from the solid surface. Giles *et al.*³⁴ studied Janus Red B on silica from water at 30 and 50°, and Lissamine Green BN on chromatographic alumina at 20 and 42°, and found increased adsorption at higher temperature. The endothermic nature of these systems has been explained on the basis of the transfer of aggregates of the solutes from solution to the surface.

Fig. 3A shows the adsorption of EB on silica in the presence of 0.5 mol dm⁻³ of KCl at different temperatures. The adsorption isotherm in the presence of KCl is obviously different from that obtained in the absence of KCl. The adsorption of EB on silica increases linearly with the [EB]. Bansal³⁵ showed that the adsorption isotherms of Co-salt on natural soils in the studied range of [Co-salt] are linear. The adsorption of EB in presence of salt is thermoneutral (identical isotherms) in the temperature range of 30–40°. The adsorption density decreases above 40°, and at 50 and 55°, the adsorption isotherms are again thermoneutral.

Fig. 3A. Adsorption isotherm for EB-silica system in aqueous KCl (0.5 mol dm⁻³) medium at different temperatures : (1) 323 and 328, (2) 303, 308 and 313 K; points for 328 and 313 K are not shown to avoid overlapping with those at other temperatures.

Fig. 3B represents the adsorption of EB on silica in the temperature range 20–50° at pH 9.2. At 20°, the curve is sigmoidal and saturation reaches at equilibrium concentration of 2.1×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³. Similar adsorption isotherm was observed for the acrylamide/montmorillonite adsorbate/adsorbent systems³⁶. With the rise in temperature, saturation is not attained and the adsorption decreases. The adsorption process is retarded in the presence of the salt, KCl (Fig. 3C). The increase in salt (ionic strength) decreases the attractive interaction between the cationic dye and the negative silica surface thereby disfavoring the process of adsorption. The adsorption process is, therefore, not favoured.

Fig. 3B. Adsorption isotherm for EB-silica system at pH 9.2 and at different temperatures : (1) 323, (2) 313, (3) 293, (4) 303 K.

Similar retardation of adsorption of dyes and polymers on solid surfaces in salt environment has been reported in the past^{37,38}. On the other hand, the adsorption of MB on silica at pH 9.2 has produced anomalous and fairly irreproducible results, and are, therefore, not considered for analysis.

Fig. 3C. Adsorption isotherm for EB-silica system at pH 9.2 and at different [KCl] : (1) 0.40, (2) 0.20, (3) 0.10, (4) 0.05, (5) 0.025 mol dm⁻³.

In the studied range of adsorption of pure EB on silica surface at pH 7.0, the process has linearly increased with adsorbate concentration. The adsorption process has been found to decrease with increasing temperature. The adsorption of pure MB on silica at pH 7.0 has been also observed to decrease with temperature and the isotherms are found to be of cooperative in nature.

The salt KCl has resulted the adsorption isotherms (MB/silica) to be of cooperative type (Fig. 3D). Puri *et al.*³⁹ studied the adsorption of phenol from aqueous solution on car-

Fig. 3D. Adsorption isotherm for MB-silica system from aqueous KCl (0.5 mol dm⁻³) medium at different temperatures : (1) 328, (2) 323, (3) 303, (4) 308, (5) 313 K.

bon blacks and found that the isotherms have shown a well-defined 'knee or plateau' and a sharp rise thereafter, indicating completion of monolayer and commencement of multilayers. They applied the modified BET equation on the system. We have been interested to examine the adsorption of both EB and MB in the light of the BET equation³⁹.

The plots of C_e/C_0 against $\frac{C_e}{x/m(C_e - C_0)}$ in the case of MB

(where C_0 is the maximum solubility of MB) in presence of salt on silica at different temperatures have yielded negative slopes. Similar plots for the EB adsorption on silica have produced straight lines parallel to the abscissa. The BET equation is thus not valid for the studied adsorbate/adsorbent systems. Although the dyes (especially AO and EB) can form stacks on the silica surface cooperatively, the adsorption of EB herein studied does not lead to multilayer formation as rationalized in the BET model.

Adsorption of EB and MB from their 1 : 1 mixture : Fig. 4A illustrates the adsorption isotherms of EB at differ-

Fig. 4A. Adsorption isotherm for EB on silica from (1 : 1 mol/mol) mixture with MB in aqueous medium at different temperatures : (1) 328, (2) 303 and 308, (3) 313, (4) 323 K.

ent temperatures from equimolar mixture with MB. In the presence of MB, silica shows increase in adsorption of EB in the temperature range 30–50° and decreases thereafter. In the case of pure EB, the adsorption is enhanced in the temperature range 30–40°.

The adsorption isotherms at different temperatures of MB from its equimolar mixture with EB are illustrated in Fig. 4B. The adsorption at 40° is higher than that at 30°. Equal extents of adsorption are observed at 40 and 50°, which declines at 55°. This behaviour is similar to that observed in the case of pure MB. Schneider *et al.*⁴⁰ observed a decrease in adsorption at higher temperature in the cases of aliphatic acids and alcohols on polystyrene. The adsorption of dye on graphon⁴¹ carried out at temperature higher than 50° has indicated a similar decrease in adsorption.

Fig. 4B. Adsorption isotherm for MB on silica from (1 : 1 mol/mol) mixture with EB in aqueous medium at different temperatures: (1) 328, (2) 303, (3) 308, (4) 313 and 323 K.

Fig. 5A represents the adsorption isotherms of EB from the 1 : 1 mixture in presence of 0.5 mol dm⁻³ KCl at differ-

Fig. 5A. Adsorption isotherm for EB silica from (1 : 1 mol/mol) mixture with MB in aqueous KCl (0.5 mol dm⁻³) medium at different temperatures : (1) 328, (2) 323, (3) 303 and 308, (4) 313 K.

ent temperatures. The presence of salt changes the nature of the curves. In the presence of KCl, pure EB results isotherms which are linear and the extents of adsorption do not vary up to 40°. The process declines above this temperature. It is seen in Fig. 5A that at 50°, the initial portion of the isotherm shows lower adsorption density than that at 55° up to the equilibrium concentration of 2.7×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³; afterwards, the adsorption density is higher^{31,42}.

Fig. 5B represents the adsorption isotherms of MB from its 1 : 1 mixture with EB at 0.5 mol dm⁻³ KCl at different temperatures. The presence of salt changes the nature of the curves also; they show mild cooperative characteristics. Similar types of isotherms were obtained by Youssef *et al.*⁴³ for water adsorption on some carbons prepared in N₂ atmosphere. The adsorption increases with temperature starting from 30°; after 40°, it decreases.

Fig. 5B. Adsorption isotherm for MB on silica from (1 : 1 mol/mol) mixture with EB in aqueous KCl (0.5 mol dm⁻³) medium at different temperatures : (1) 328, (2) 323, (3) 303, (4) 308, (5) 313 K.

The adsorption of EB from its 1 : 1 (mol/mol) mixture with MB at pH 7.0 is, on the whole, linear, whereas that of MB under the same condition is again cooperative. The adsorption in both the cases are exothermic.

Combined adsorption of EB and MB on silica : The combined adsorption of EB and MB on the silica surface in aqueous and 0.5 mol dm⁻³ KCl solution at different temperatures are illustrated in Figs. 6A and 6B. In the absence of KCl, the isotherms are Langmuirian type and the phenomenon is endothermic at 30 and 40°; it is thermoneutral at 40 and 50° and exothermic at 55°. In this behaviour, the combined adsorption differs from the individual adsorption in the case of EB. In the presence of 0.5 mol dm⁻³ KCl, the isotherms tend to become moderately cooperative. They show endothermicity in the range 30–40°; thereafter in the range

Fig. 6A. Isotherm for combined adsorption of EB and MB (1 : 1 mol/mol) on silica from aqueous medium at different temperatures: (1) 328, (2) 303, (3) 308, (4) 323 and 313 K.

Fig. 6B. Isotherm for combined adsorption of EB and MB (1 : 1 mol/mol) on silica from aqueous KCl (0.5 mol dm⁻³) medium at different temperatures : (1) 328, (2) 323, (3) 303, (4) 308, (5) 313 K.

of 40–55°, they are exothermic. The thermoneutral phenomenon is absent in the salt (KCl) medium. At comparable equilibrium dye concentration, the extent of adsorption is less in the presence of the salt. The individual pure dyes have also shown nearly cooperative adsorption isotherms at different temperatures in KCl environment.

Surface and solution composition of the dyes : In the binary mixtures, 1 : 1 molar composition of EB and MB has been used for their adsorption study on silica surface. It would be worthwhile to look into their compositions on the surface and in solution under the condition of adsorption equilibrium. The results at 30° are presented in Table 1. The other temperatures have shown similar results and hence are not presented. It is found that the molefraction compositions of EB on the surface is lower than that in solution whereas that of MB is higher. On the whole, surface composition of MB is greater than that of EB at all concentrations. Moreover, while X_{EB}^{Surf} decreases with increasing total

Table 1. Molefraction composition of EB and MB in solution and on silica surface

X_{EB}^{Sol}	X_{EB}^{Surf}	X_{MB}^{Sol}	X_{MB}^{Surf}
0.65	0.47	0.35	0.53
0.67	0.47	0.33	0.54
0.69	0.46	0.31	0.54
0.66	0.45	0.34	0.55
0.65	0.44	0.35	0.56
0.60	0.46	0.40	0.55
0.58	0.44	0.43	0.56

concentration of the dye, X_{MB}^{Surf} increases. The enhanced adsorption of MB displaced EB from the silica surface. This is considered due to the increased self-interaction (aggregation) of EB in solution than on the surface. It is interesting to note that at no concentration, 1 : 1 composition of EB and MB has been found to exist in the adsorption process, either it is higher as for EB or is lower as for MB.

Treatment of the adsorption data : It is known that localized adsorption with monolayer formation and 1 : 1 correspondence between the adsorbate molecules on energetically homogeneous adsorption sites obeys the Langmuir isotherm. In the present study wherever applicable, the adsorption results have been analyzed in the light of the Langmuir equation (shown below) and typical Langmuir plots are shown in Figs. 7 and 8.

Fig. 7. Langmuir plot for the adsorption of pure EB on silica in aqueous medium at different temperatures : (1) 313, (2) 303, (3) 323, (4) 328 K.

The Langmuir equation

$$\frac{m}{x} = \frac{1}{x_m} + \left(\frac{1}{x_m k'} \right) \frac{1}{C_e} \quad (1)$$

Fig. 8. Langmuir plot for the adsorption of MB on silica from (1 : 1 mol/mol) mixture with EB in aqueous medium at different temperatures (1) 313, (2) 318, (3) 313, (4) 328 K

where x is the mole of dye adsorbed at equilibrium, m , the mass of the adsorbent, x_m , the monolayer dye adsorption density (mol g^{-1}), k' , the equilibrium constant for the adsorption process, and C_e , the equilibrium concentration of the dye (mol dm^{-3}). The intercept and the slope of the linear plot between $(x/m)^{-1}$ and C_e^{-1} are expected to provide the values of x_m and k' . The x_m and k' values obtained for the studied system (pure EB and MB, and their 1 : 1 mixtures in absence of salt) are given in Tables 2 and 3. The $\ln k'$ values for the adsorption of EB in pure and mixed condition are lower than MB, and the x_m values are greater in pure condition but lower in mixed condition. On the basis of monolayer adsorption, the specific surface area of the silica obtained from the x_m values of MB (taking area per MB molecule = 120 \AA^2)⁴⁴ is $16.41 \text{ S/m}^2\text{g}^{-1}$.

Thermodynamics of adsorption of EB and MB : From the adsorption isotherms obtained at different temperatures, the thermodynamic parameter, the standard enthalpy change (ΔH_{ad}^0) for adsorption can be evaluated using the van't Hoff equation,

$$\ln k' = \text{constant} - \frac{\Delta H_{\text{ad}}^0}{RT} \quad (2)$$

The van't Hoff plots are not exhibited to save space. There occur changes in the direction of the slopes of the linear plots suggesting that the process of adsorption may occur both exo- and endothermally. A similar duality in van't Hoff enthalpy has been shown by substrate binding to human leukocytic elastase⁴⁵. Sharp breaks in the van't Hoff plots in the temperature range 40–50° have been observed. The endothermicity in the adsorption process was reported by Khairy *et al.*⁴⁶. The adsorption of bile salts on graphite was reported to be also endothermic⁴⁷. The desorption of orga-

Table 2. Adsorption characteristics of pure MB and EB from aqueous solution on silica at different temperatures

Temp K	$\ln k'$	$-\Delta G_{\text{ad}}^0$ (kJ mol^{-1})	ΔS_{ad}^0 ($\text{J mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$)
	MB(EB)	MB(EB)	MB(EB)
303	12.3 (10.25)	31.0 (25.8)	402 (135)
308	13.0 (10.25)	33.4 (25.8)	403 (135)
313	13.5 (10.4)	35.2 (27.1)	402 (134)
323	13.5 (10.0)	35.2 (26.9)	402 (-19.6)
328	— (9.8)	— (26.8)	— (-19.8)
		MB (EB)	
$10^5 x_m$ (mol g^{-1})		2.27 (3.57)	
ΔH_{ad}^0 ($\text{kJ K}^{-1}\text{mol}^{-1}$)		90.7 (-33.9)	
		— (15)	

Two sets of ΔH_{ad}^0 for MB and EB are due to exothermicity and endothermicity of the process of their adsorption on silica surface

Table 3. Adsorption characteristics of MB (EB) from their 1 : 1 mixture in aqueous solution on silica at different temperatures

Temp K	$\ln k'$	$-\Delta G_{\text{ad}}^0$ (kJ mol^{-1})	ΔS_{ad}^0 ($\text{J mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$)
	MB(EB)	MB(EB)	MB(EB)
303	11.6 (10.7)	29.1 (27.0)	473 (241)
308	11.7 (10.7)	30.0 (27.0)	468 (241)
313	13.0 (11.5)	34.0 (29.8)	473 (242)
323	13.0 (11.8)	34.0 (31.6)	473 (240)
328	10.9 (10.3)	29.7 (28.1)	-315 (-611)
		MB (EB)	
$10^5 x_m$ (mol g^{-1})		1.8 (1.6)	
ΔH_{ad}^0 ($\text{kJ K}^{-1}\text{mol}^{-1}$)		114 (45.9)	
		-133 (-229)	

Two sets of ΔH_{ad}^0 for MB and EB are due to exothermicity and endothermicity of the process of their adsorption on silica surface

nized water on the silica surface at higher temperature eventually enhances the adsorption process (synergistically or cooperatively) resulting endothermicity to this physical phenomenon. The low magnitudes of the ΔH_{ad}^0 rule out the occurrence of chemisorption.

The change in the standard Gibbs free energy of adsorption (ΔG_{ad}^0) has been obtained from the relation,

$$\Delta G_{\text{ad}}^0 = -RT \ln k' \quad (3)$$

and the standard entropy change (ΔS_{ad}^0) has been from the Gibbs-Helmholtz equation,

$$\Delta S_{\text{ad}}^0 = \frac{\Delta H_{\text{ad}}^0 - \Delta G_{\text{ad}}^0}{T} \quad (4)$$

The ΔG_{ad}^0 and ΔS_{ad}^0 values obtained for the system studied are listed in Tables 1 and 2. Positive ΔS_{ad}^0 was reported by

Schneider *et al.*⁴⁰ for the adsorption of aliphatic acids and alcohols on polystyrene. The present results indicate favourable hydrophobic interaction of the dye molecules with the silica surface at higher temperature. It is supported by the negative entropy changes. Association, fixation and immobilization of the dye on silica and that of the solvent molecules consequent of adsorption resulted in a loss of entropy of the system. The $+ΔH_{ad}^0$ supports the removal of surface associated water molecules making room for favorable dye adsorption. The removal of solvent molecules and their reorganization after the dye adsorption lead to an overall positive enthalpy change. The overall ordering of the system (mainly stemming from dye aggregation on the silica surface) at temperatures $≥323$ K is reflected on $-ΔS_{ad}^0$ as in the case of hydrophobic interaction. On the other hand, up to the temperature of 313 K, the $ΔS_{ad}^0$ is positive. The adsorption of the non or weakly aggregated dye molecules on the silica surface releases solvent molecules into solution. The observed positive $ΔH_{ad}^0$ and $ΔS_{ad}^0$ values indicate entropy gain to be the driving force for the adsorption; the $TΔS_{ad}^0$ is obviously appreciably greater than $ΔH_{ad}^0$. This difference is more for MB than EB under the studied experimental conditions.

Conclusions :

(i) Both EB and MB get adsorbed on silica surface from aqueous solution following Langmuir isotherm. The adsorption process shows exo- and endothermicity as well as thermoneutrality in specific ranges of temperature. In presence of the salt KCl, the nature of the isotherms becomes, on the whole, non-Langmuirian and cooperative type. (ii) In 1 : 1 (mol/mol) mixed condition, both the dyes are adsorbed on the silica surface from aqueous and aqueous KCl media again showing exothermicity, endothermicity and thermoneutrality. (iii) The extent of adsorption and the nature of the isotherms of the dyes (EB and MB) are pH-dependent. At pH 9.2, the adsorption of MB on silica is nonsystematic. (iv) The combined adsorption of EB and MB on silica is also Langmuirian, and shows features comparable to their individual adsorption. The surface concentration of EB is lower than that in solution whereas that of MB is higher on the surface than in solution. (v) The energetics of the adsorption process are mostly entropy-controlled and reflect the interplay of both electrostatic and nonpolar (hydrophobic) interactions.

Experimental

Chromatographic grade silica (SRL, India), used as the adsorbent, contained sieved particles of 100–200 mesh (activity = 2.3, pH of a 10% aqueous suspension = 7). Prior to use, the samples were heated at 300° for 4 h and then cooled

in a desiccator (~12 h).

The dyes ethidium bromide (2,7-diamino-10-ethyl-9-phenylphenanthridium bromide, EB) (Sigma) and methylene blue (3,9-bisdimethylaminophenazothionium chloride, MB) (E. Merck) were high purity products and used as received.

A Shimadzu 160A UV-vis spectrophotometer was employed for absorbance measurements using silica cells of path length 1 cm.

Double-distilled conductivity water was used for solution preparation. All measurements were taken at constant temperature ($±0.1^∘$).

Stock solutions of dyes (EB and MB) and electrolyte (KCl) were prepared in double-distilled conductivity water and stored. Experimental solutions of the desired concentrations were obtained by appropriate dilution. In the adsorption experiment, weighed quantities of the silica (0.1 g) were taken in a series of standard-joint pyrex glass stoppered bottles (25 ml) and to each of them 20 ml of the dye solution with varying initial concentration (C_i) was added. The bottles were covered with black paper to protect them from the action of light on the dye, and were shaken in a horizontal shaker for 2 h, and then placed to equilibrate in a thermostated water-bath at the desired temperature with intermittent shaking for a period of 16–20 h. It may be mentioned that the equilibrium time required for different systems may vary from system to system. It has been reported that the equilibrium for the adsorption of basic dyes is usually attained in a few minutes at room temperature. We found that the dye/silica system required ~1 h to attain equilibrium. But we allowed much longer time (~24 h) to the system to safeguard against the nonattainment of equilibration. After the attainment of equilibrium, 5 ml aliquots were withdrawn from the bottles and centrifuged, and 3 ml of each of the solutions were used for spectrophotometric estimation. The amount (mole) of dye (x) adsorbed per g of silica was calculated the difference in the initial concentration (C_i) and the equilibrium concentration (C_e) applying the equation,

$$\frac{x}{m} = \frac{(C_i - C_e)20}{1000 m}$$

where m is the mass of the adsorbent.

The equilibrium concentration of the dye in each experiment was calculated from the maximum absorbance with the known molar extinction coefficient of the dye. The maximum absorbance (λ_{max}) of EB and MB in the aqueous medium were 481 and 664 nm, respectively. There occurred no change in the λ_{max} in different pH medium. The concentrations of the experimental solutions were observed to obey

the Beer-Lambert's law with molar extinction coefficients (ϵ) of 1.1×10^4 and $6.25 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for EB and MB, respectively. There was no change in the ϵ at pH 7. At pH 9.2, the observed value of ϵ for EB was $5.56 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. There was no change of ϵ in different media for the binary mixtures of the two dyes. The effect of temperature was minor on the ϵ of the dyes in the working range of temperature 20–55°.

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